

defies the neat dichotomy of “education for immigration” and “immigration for education,” emerging as an interactive process involving humans (migrants, non-migrants, hosts) and non-humans (policies, technology, states) within the broader context of power, historical legacies, and everyday interactions. The interplay among these aspects reveals the multiplicity of their liminality, i.e., as a student, immigrant, non-resident Bangladeshi, and part-time worker, shaping individuals’ meaning-making process and rendering well-being a concept perpetually “in-making.” This fluidity and dynamic definition of well-being highlights the shifting aspirations and migration motivations while challenging the initial colonial-inflected visions of a ‘better life in the West.’ Therefore, education migration constitutes an ongoing, relational endeavor of becoming, and by tracing how these migrants occupy—and seek to transcend—forms of liminality, this research enriches anthropological debates on transnational mobility, power, and identity.

Researching Cancer among African migrants in Finland

Perpetual Crentsil, *University of Helsinki*

This paper discusses conducting research on cancer among African migrants in Finland. It examines methods for data collection, privacy and confidentiality issues that also show cancer as a disease—a process—embedded in social practices, perceptions and spaces within mundane social structures as well as relations that affect each other in interesting ways. Respondents’ notions about cancer also express ideas outside of clinical/biomedical explanations. There are various sites of belonging and not belonging that legitimise or contest one frame of reference over another and affect the research procedure. Intersectionality and regimes of practices based on demographic, social, economic, gender, and cultural variables affect notions about cancer even as confidentiality and ethical considerations also influence the researcher’s positionality, data collection and methods for knowing. Secrecy and privacy about cancer also compares with researching HIV/AIDS in Ghana/Africa. This paper is based on an ethnographic research on cancer prevalence and complications among African migrants in Finland (and on my previous study of HIV/AIDS in Ghana) using participant observation, unstructured interviews and conversations as well as a questionnaire survey for data collection. Keywords: cancer; perceptions; HIV/AIDS; confidentiality; positionality; African migrants; Finland.

Minorities’ perceptions and anxieties about policing during covid-19 in Finland

Stephen Egharevba; Perpetual Crentsil; *University of Helsinki*

Many research studies have premised that ethnicity or minority status is one of the most striking factors producing apprehension or dissatisfaction with the police. This paper discusses African and Asian migrants’ perceptions and anxieties about policing during the COVID-19 period in Finland. Migrants often bring unique perceptions and anxieties that contribute to their vulnerability within the broader society. The findings in this study indicate that most of the respondents are concerned about the police based on their anxieties or perceptions which influence certain attitudes towards the police, whether negative or positive. This paper argues that minorities, often marginalised in societal hierarchies, perceive bias in police attitudes and behaviours, which they view as reflective of the broader Finnish policing ideology. Keywords: COVID-19, policing, anxieties, perceptions, migrants in Finland.

Panel 4: Tensing Senses: Comparing/contrasting participant observation & sensory methods – Part 1

Mari Korpela, Roger Norum

In the practice and imagination of anthropology, participant observation has long been at the core of both how anthropologists collect their data and how anthropological knowledge is generated. At the same time, while sensory methods are clearly having a moment, a number of the discipline's constituent "novel" methodological approaches (e.g. ecoacoustics, visual or tactile tools, artistic interventions) have themselves historical roots that indeed date back well over a century. Reflecting critically on the compulsion researchers often feel to innovate and invent 'novel' research methods, this panel reflects on what is actually being gained by explicitly including sensory methods in the anthropological toolkit. How does the data generated by such approaches compare with "traditional", tried-and-tested ethnographic research? How much does methodological experimentation actually add to our work (considering that anthropological textual output is often evaluated via rather conservative metrics)? Is classical participant observation best understood as the very essence of what anthropology does, or should it be seen rather as a point of departure for a discipline that desperately needs to evolve? This panel welcomes papers that critically elaborate on various traditional anthropological and newer sensory ethnographic practice, considering distinct methodological approaches and experiments.

Panel 4 Papers:

"I need to feel what they feel". Exploring touch with sensory research methods

Maria Nätyнки, *University of Oulu*

Two articles (one published, one half-completed) draw on my ongoing doctoral research project 'Embracing wind, calming water, and healing rope'. Pleasure through touch in multisensory more-than-human relations. The project explores human – more-than-human touch within selected groups of people who form meaningful and pleasure-giving sensual relationships with natural bodies and making worlds by these sensory engagements. The first article reveals three women's more-than-human tactile companionships with trees and water. The second article will uncover how naturists are seeking tactile more-than-human pleasures from nudity. I consider touch as more-than-human tactile entanglements, which offers a novel perspective on gendered and sexualised bodily 'becomings'.

In this presentation, I will critically elaborate on how I briefly entangled with these peoples' tactile entanglements in certain places, times, and materialities with the sensory ethnography research methods used: go along interviews, thick participation, and touch walking. The latter is my hybrid 'experiencing-with method', created from existing walking methods previously used to explore olfaction and soundscapes. I also collected 'touch biographies', written accounts, where the participants recall their touch histories, to enrich the empirical data. I also wrote pages of field notes to capture the course of events and self-reflection. I claim that there are many strengths of the experiencing-with method. It attuned my body to haptic knowledge of natural bodies, multisensory impressions of the environment and affective engagements with the natural bodies in a way that extends beyond words. However, it can be still questioned whether these 'novel' methods are just revamped versions of participant observation.

Sensing farming landscapes

Galina Kallio; Will LaFleur; *University of Helsinki*

The everyday and long-term practices of small-scale agroecological farmers are, at their core, profoundly sensory. Farmers sink their hands into the soil, examining its smell, texture and life through touch, sight, and smell; they move along rows of diverse crops, looking, touching, and tasting to discern what is growing, what is thriving, and what is struggling. These embodied practices are deeply attuned to the rhythms of the landscape, whether or not an ethnographer is present to label them as such. The role of the ethnographer, however, is not to impose a definition but to illuminate the inherent sensuousness of such work—to narrate and detail the material world in which farmers dwell and correspond. In doing so, s/he reveals the practical concerns of farming as inseparable from broader socio-ecological, economic, technological, and political contexts. As the ecological crises intensify, these farmers are increasingly viewed through two dominant frames: as agents of carbon sequestration, and as key informants in understanding the attentive, more-than-human relationships and sense-abilities of nonhuman species. Yet, both perspectives lean heavily on natural scientific representations—modeling carbon flows, visualizing microbial life under the soil—relying on methods that render these processes shapeless, odorless, tasteless, soundless, and invisible to the human eye. In doing so, they paradoxically sideline the sensory ways of knowing that are integral to farming landscapes. We propose a critical re-examination of the sensory and its role in ethnography, particularly in capturing the aliveness, sense-ability, and multispecies entanglements that define more-than-human worlds. By tracing these sensory dimensions, we seek to restore attention to the embodied, sensuous practices that constitute farming, raising a conversation about bringing the sensory back into the foreground of how we understand and engage with farming landscapes that are always and inherently more-than-human. ^{OBJ}

Resonating fields: soil bioacoustic in multi-species ethnography

Rye Hickman; Valerie Nelson, *University of Greenwich*

This paper examines how soil bioacoustics, an emerging method for conservation monitoring, offers both complementary and contrasting approaches to ethnographic knowledge production. Drawing on fieldwork that combines classical participant observation with acoustic monitoring of soil ecosystems, this research demonstrates how sensory methods can enhance conventional anthropological approaches. By comparing data gathered through human-centred participant observation with bioacoustic recordings of soil organisms, this study reveals the methodological tensions and opportunities that emerge when bridging natural science techniques with anthropological inquiry.

The paper analyses three key comparisons: first, between the temporal and spatial scales accessible through participant observation versus bioacoustic monitoring; second, between the types of relationships and interactions revealed through each method; and third, between the forms of knowledge produced when combining these approaches. Through detailed examination of agricultural and conservation field sites, the research demonstrates how bioacoustic methods can capture otherwise imperceptible multi-species interactions while simultaneously contextualizing these findings within broader social and cultural frameworks revealed through traditional ethnographic engagement.

This methodological innovation contributes to ongoing debates about the evolution of anthropological methods by showing how sensory approaches can expand the discipline's comparative capabilities without abandoning its foundational techniques. The paper argues that soil bioacoustics, when integrated with participant observation, enables a more nuanced understanding of human-environmental relations while also challenging anthropology to reconsider its methodological assumptions. This comparison of methods ultimately reveals how different forms of

attention and documentation can generate complementary insights into the complex relationships between human and non-human actors in more-than-human soil relational webs.

Sensing the river: innovative designs for more-than-human research

Catrien Notermans; Anke Tonnaer; *Radboud University*

This paper explores how to expand our 'traditional' methodological toolbox for ethnographic fieldwork beyond the human. Methods of collecting and representing ethnographic data, generally, take spoken language and written reports as the fundamental ways of transmitting knowledge. These are essentially anthropocentric and logocentric, and thus tend to disregard the knowledge gained from sensorily connecting beyond the human (Gatt & Lembo 2022). Post-anthropocentric scholarship, however, explicitly asks for such embodied knowledge. Our paper addresses the question of how sensory methods combined with artistic design and participatory research may help us to incorporate more-than-human actors in our ethnographic research, to connect and create familiarity with 'nature' bodies and subsequently listen to these other-than-human 'voices'. We critically reflect on our methodological experiments that were meant to collect new narratives on more-than-human relations in the multi-sensory landscape of the river Waal in the Netherlands, one of the country's largest rivers, flowing from Germany to the North Sea. In reaction to dominant anthropocentric hydraulic discourses we experimented with multimodal artistic design to make the Waal tangible as a living body and to give expression to the unwritten affect and attachment people foster for the river. These experiments were done together with the river Waal, students of Anthropology at Radboud University, and citizens of the city of Nijmegen, the town for which the Waal is the central body of water. Our paper presents the insights of the experiments and reflects on what we gained by including these sensory and artistic methods in our anthropological toolbox.

Panel 6: Negative Capability and Productive Uncertainty in Crises of Closure – Part 1

Kenneth Sillander, Ivan Tacey, Isabell Herrmans

This panel explores the productive potential of Indigenous Peoples' open ways of life and their embodiment of "negative capability" in contemporary crises of closure. John Keats' concept of negative capability – "the ability to remain in uncertainties, mysteries, and doubts without the irritable reaching after fact and reason" – is adopted to reframe Indigenous challenges and conditions for resilience. Beyond viewing negative capability merely as an intellectual capacity to dwell in uncertainty and embrace ambiguity, we propose extending it to Indigenous Peoples' (and other marginalized groups') often profound practical abilities to bear with precariousness and hardship and make do with available material resources. Historically, endemic socio- political, economic and environmental uncertainties have prompted many Indigenous groups to develop markedly flexible traits and pronounced "orientations of openness" as means of creative adaptation (e.g., fluid socialities, diversified subsistence strategies, relational inclusiveness, eclecticism, opportunism, and pragmatism). However, the distinct nature of their contemporary conditions – such as environmental degradation, land dispossession, commodification and state- driven schemes of inscription and purification – pose unique challenges to their established lifeways. The challenges arise as growing